

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC RELATIONS FUNCTIONS IN DRIVING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

This study explores the pivotal role of public relations (PR) in advancing development initiatives across both social and economic sectors. The importance of PR in shaping public perceptions, building strategic relationships and facilitating effective communication between organisations and their stakeholders is well-established. However, there remains a significant research gap in understanding the specific functions of PR in the context of development and its impact on achieving desired outcomes. The study addresses this gap by conducting a comparative analysis of PR functions and their contributions to development efforts. The primary objective is to unravel how PR strategies influence the success of development initiatives and to identify the key factors that contribute to their effectiveness. The study reviews various case studies and best practices from the developed and developing countries, focusing on common patterns, challenges and success factors that can inform future PR strategies in the development sector. The study is grounded in the Excellence Theory of Public Relations, adopting a library-based research method to analyse existing literature and empirical works. The findings show that under specific conditions, PR is most effective in driving social and economic development, while also offering practical recommendations for leveraging PR to enhance development outcomes. The study underscores the potential of PR as a strategic tool in development efforts, advocating for its integration into broader development strategies to foster sustainable growth. The research also contributes valuable insights for PR professionals, policymakers, and development practitioners, aiming to bridge the gap between PR practices and development studies. The study confirms PR's

strategic role in fostering social and economic development, emphasising stakeholder engagement and context-specific strategies. Cross-cultural PR effectiveness, digital PR's impact and long-term measurement of PR's development outcomes warrant deeper exploration to enhance its integration into sustainable growth frameworks.

Keywords: Public Relations (PR), Social Development, Economic Development, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Comparative Study.

Introduction

Public relations (PR) has grown into a strategic discipline, extending its influence beyond corporate communication to shaping societal outcomes and economic policies. Today, PR functions are increasingly recognised for their capacity to contribute to social and economic development by fostering relationships, enhancing reputation and engaging communities. As economies evolve and societies face complex challenges, public relations plays a key role in bridging gaps between institutions and the public, facilitating development-driven communication and promoting trust between stakeholders (Cutlip, *et al* 2006).

In many regions, particularly in developing countries, public relations are crucial in addressing socio-economic disparities and fostering inclusive growth. Strategic PR efforts can enhance the effectiveness of development initiatives by advocating for social causes, improving public engagement and promoting corporate social responsibility (CSR). Moreover, PR practitioners contribute to shaping policy frameworks and public opinion, positioning PR as a critical driver of sustainable development (Verčič & Grunig, 2000). As governments, corporations and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) alike engage in efforts to promote economic advancement and social well-being, PR plays an essential role in communicating these efforts and influencing public perception.

This study examines the impact of public relations functions on social and economic development, focusing on a comparative analysis of PR practices across different sectors or regions like the USA, the United Kingdom, Nigeria and Kenya. By analysing PR strategies used to promote economic initiatives, address social challenges and build trust, the researchers explored how PR contributes to fostering an enabling environment for development. The study also aims to highlight regional or sectoral differences in PR practices, shedding light on how context-specific factors influence the effectiveness of PR in driving development outcomes. It is hoped that through this comparative study, this research will contribute to understanding the critical role public relations plays in supporting social and economic development, particularly in emerging markets. It will also identify best practices and provide insights into how PR functions can be optimised to further enhance development efforts in different socio-political contexts.

Statement of the Problem

Public relations (PR) has increasingly been recognised as a strategic tool not only in managing corporate reputation but also in shaping the broader socio-economic landscape (Verčič & Grunig, 2000). However, the direct impact of PR functions on driving social and economic development remains underexplored, particularly in the context of emerging markets and developing nations. While there is a general understanding of PR's role in facilitating communication between organisations and the public, its contribution to sustainable development initiatives, poverty reduction and social equity has not been comprehensively studied (Molleda & Ferguson, 2004). This gap is significant given the growing need for effective communication strategies in addressing global challenges such as inequality, climate change and economic disparity.

In various regions, including Africa, Asia and Latin America, public relations practitioners are engaged in development-related communication efforts. Governments, NGOs, and private-sector entities increasingly rely on PR to engage communities, disseminate critical information, and promote social change. However, the effectiveness of these efforts in delivering measurable socio-economic outcomes remains unclear. Moreover, the specific PR strategies that work best in different socio-political and cultural contexts are still largely unknown (Sriramesh & Vercic, 2009). This lack of empirical evidence creates a challenge for PR professionals and policymakers who aim to use communication as a catalyst for development.

Furthermore, much of the existing literature on public relations has focused predominantly on its corporate applications, with limited attention to its role in public-sector communication and social change (Heath & Coombs, 2006). As a result, there is a pressing need for research that examines how PR functions can be optimised to support broader development goals, such as improving education, health and economic conditions in underdeveloped regions. This study seeks to address this gap by conducting a comparative analysis of public relations practices across different sectors and regions, on their impact on social and economic development.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of public relations (PR) functions in driving social and economic development through a comparative analysis of various regions and sectors. Specifically, the study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. To analyse the role of public relations in promoting social development initiatives
2. To evaluate the contribution of public relations to economic development efforts

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide this study:

1. How does public relations contribute to the promotion of social development initiatives?
2. What is the impact of public relations on economic development efforts across different sectors?

Theoretical Framework for the Study

The theoretical framework for this study on the impact of public relations (PR) functions in driving social and economic development draws from a blend of communication, development and public relations theories. These frameworks will provide the conceptual foundation needed to understand how PR strategies are employed to influence developmental outcomes, both socially and economically and contribute to sustainable development goals across different sectors and regions.

1. Development Communication Theory

Another key theoretical framework is development communication theory, which focuses on the role of communication in promoting social and economic progress. Development communication, also known as “communication for development” (C4D), emphasises the use of strategic communication to support human development, often focusing on marginalised communities in developing nations (Servaes, 2008). The theory emerged in the 1950s–1960s, primarily through the works of Daniel Lerner, Everett Rogers and Wilbur Schramm, who linked mass communication to socioeconomic progress in post-colonial nations (Servaes, 1999). Daniel Lerner (1958) introduced foundational ideas in *The Passing of Traditional Society*, arguing that mass media exposure fosters modernisation by promoting empathy and aspirational change (Lerner, 1958). Everett Rogers (1962) expanded the theory in *Diffusion of Innovations*, emphasising how communication drives the adoption of new technologies and practices in developing societies (Rogers, 1962). Wilbur Schramm (1964) formalised the theory in *Mass Media and National Development*, advocating media as a tool for education and governance (Schramm, 1964).

The theory was institutionalised through UNESCO and U.S. development agencies, though later critiques (e.g., participatory communication) challenged its top-down approach (Melkote & Steeves, 2015). This theory posits that communication catalyses change, helping to disseminate information, shift behaviours and promote participation in development initiatives. In this study, development communication theory will be used to examine how PR functions facilitate information dissemination and mobilise public support for social and economic development initiatives. For example, public health campaigns or financial literacy programmes often rely on development communication principles to encourage behaviour change and foster economic empowerment.

2. Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984) emphasises the importance of managing relationships with a variety of stakeholders, each of whom has an interest in the organisation's actions. In the context of social and economic development, stakeholders may include governments, non-governmental organisations, businesses, community groups and international organisations. PR practitioners play a critical role in engaging these diverse groups, ensuring that their perspectives are considered and that they remain aligned with development objectives. This study will apply stakeholder theory to explore how PR functions as a mediator between different development stakeholders, facilitating collaboration and ensuring that development initiatives meet the needs of all parties involved. Effective stakeholder management is critical for ensuring the success and sustainability of development programmes.

The theoretical frameworks discussed above are complementary and will be integrated into this study to provide a robust understanding of the role of public relations in driving social and economic development. The two-way symmetrical model provides insight into the importance of dialogue and participatory communication in development, while development communication theory emphasises the strategic role of communication in achieving development goals. Social capital theory highlights the value of relationships and trust, while agenda-setting theory explains how PR functions can shape the public and policy agendas. Lastly, stakeholder theory underscores the importance of managing relationships with diverse groups to ensure the success of development initiatives. Together, these theories provide a comprehensive framework for examining how PR functions can influence social and economic development. By using this integrated approach, the study will offer a detailed analysis of how PR strategies are implemented in different sectors and how they contribute to sustainable development goals.

Conceptual Review

Public Relations (PR) has evolved into a strategic tool for fostering social and economic development across different societies. The field has expanded beyond corporate and governmental communication to encompass advocacy, social change and economic transformation. This conceptual review explores the various dimensions of PR functions and their role in social and economic development, providing a comparative analysis across different regions and sectors. It integrates theoretical frameworks, empirical findings and contemporary perspectives to highlight PR's impact.

Public Relations as a Driver of Social Development

Public relations plays a crucial role in shaping public perception, driving social change, and facilitating communication between governments, organisations and the public (Grunig & Hunt, 2005). PR functions such as media relations, public affairs and crisis communication help build public trust and foster civic engagement. In democratic societies, PR campaigns have been instrumental in mobilising social movements, raising awareness of critical issues and advocating for policy change (Heath & Palenchar, 2009).

For example, in Africa, PR-driven health communication campaigns have significantly influenced behavioural change concerning public health issues such as HIV/AIDS awareness, malaria prevention and COVID-19 vaccination efforts (Okigbo, 2020). Similarly, in Western societies, PR strategies have supported gender equality movements, environmental sustainability campaigns and human rights advocacy.

Public Relations and Economic Development

PR contributes to economic development by enhancing brand reputation, fostering investor relations and promoting corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives. Organisations leverage PR strategies to build credibility, attract investments and enhance consumer confidence (Cornelissen, 2017). Government-led PR campaigns also play a role in nation branding, tourism promotion and trade facilitation (Anholt, 2010).

For instance, in Nigeria, PR has been pivotal in repositioning industries such as telecommunications, banking and oil and gas. Strategic communication has facilitated foreign direct investment (FDI) by projecting a positive business climate (Ekwueme & Akpan, 2018). Conversely, in developed economies, PR campaigns are utilised by multinational corporations to navigate global markets, manage reputational risks and align with corporate sustainability goals.

Comparative Analysis of PR Functions across Societies

The role of PR in development varies based on socio-political contexts, economic structures and media landscapes. In developed nations, PR is often driven by digital innovation, leveraging artificial intelligence (AI), big data and social media analytics for targeted messaging (Macnamara, 2016). On the other hand, in developing economies, PR relies more on traditional media, community engagement and grassroots mobilisation due to lower digital penetration rates (Nwosu & Uffoh, 2017).

A comparative study of PR in the United States and Africa reveals significant contrasts. While Western PR practices emphasise corporate transparency, media relations and crisis communication, African PR focuses more on relationship-building, storytelling and cultural sensitivities (Molleda & Roberts, 2021). Understanding these differences is essential for designing effective PR strategies tailored to specific regions.

Review of Empirical Studies

In the field of public relations (PR) and its contribution to social and economic development, several empirical studies have explored the various ways in which PR functions are deployed to achieve developmental outcomes. This review aims to synthesise the key findings from empirical studies conducted in various sectors and regions, providing a comparative analysis of the impact of PR strategies on development. The review also highlights the gaps in the literature, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria and underscores the need for further empirical research in these contexts.

Servaes & Malikhao (2008), in "Development Communication: Moving from the Physical to the Virtual," explore how communication strategies, including public relations (PR), drive social and economic development. Using a qualitative approach, they emphasise participatory communication and PR's role in fostering community engagement and development. Their findings highlight the importance of inclusive communication in achieving sustainable development. Recommendations include integrating PR into development programmes and prioritising local voices. Unlike their focus on participatory communication, this study examines PR's broader impact on social and economic development through a comparative lens.

Figuroa, et al (2002), in their work *Communication for Social Change: An Integrated Model for Measuring the Process and Its Outcomes*, explored how communication influences social change by fostering collective action. Using a conceptual model, they found that participatory communication enhances development outcomes. They recommended community-driven communication strategies. While their study focused on measuring social change, the present study examines the comparative impact of public relations functions in shaping social and economic development across different contexts.

White and Dozier (2005), in their work *Public Relations and Management Decision Making*, examined the strategic role of public relations in organisational effectiveness. Using a survey-based approach, they found that PR enhances decision-making by facilitating two-way communication between organisations and stakeholders. They concluded that PR should be integrated into management for better outcomes and recommended stronger PR evaluation metrics. While their study focused on PR in corporate settings, the present study explores its broader socio-economic impact in different societal contexts.

Onah and Nwosu (2014), in "Public Relations and National Development: The Nigerian Experience," investigated PR's role in fostering national development. Using a mixed-method approach, they highlight PR's effectiveness in promoting government policies and public engagement. Their findings reveal that strategic PR enhances trust and participation in development initiatives. Recommendations included strengthening PR frameworks and training professionals. While their study focused on Nigeria, this paper adopts a comparative approach to analyse PR's broader impact on social and economic development across multiple contexts.

Sriramesh and Vercic (2009), in "The Global Public Relations Handbook: Theory, Research and Practice," analysed PR's role in global contexts, emphasising its impact on societal and economic development. Using a multi-case study approach, they highlighted how PR fosters dialogue, builds relationships and supports development agendas. Their findings stress the need for culturally sensitive PR strategies. Recommendations included adopting global best practices and enhancing PR education. Unlike their global focus, this study compares PR's impact on development across specific social and economic contexts.

Chaka (2016), in *The Role of Public Relations in Socio-Economic Development: A Case Study of Emerging Markets*, explored how PR strategies contribute to economic growth and social change.

Using a qualitative case study approach, the study found that effective PR fosters public trust, attracts investment and enhances policy communication. Chaka concluded that PR should be leveraged for national development and recommended policy-driven PR strategies. While this study focuses on emerging markets, the present research comparatively analyses PR's impact across different socio-economic settings.

Diga and Kelleher (2009), in *Social Media Use, Perceptions of Public Relations and Public Engagement*, examined how digital PR influences public perception and engagement. Using a survey method, they found that organisations leveraging social media for PR foster stronger public trust and participation. They concluded that digital platforms are essential for modern PR strategies and recommended integrating social media analytics. While their study focuses on digital PR, the present research comparatively examines broader PR functions in socio-economic development.

Adebayo and Olatunji (2015), in "Public Relations and Sustainable Development in Nigeria," explored PR's role in promoting sustainable development. Using qualitative methods, they emphasised PR's effectiveness in fostering stakeholder engagement and policy advocacy. Their findings reveal that PR enhances transparency and public participation in development programmes. Recommendations included integrating PR into national development plans and improving PR training. While their study focused on Nigeria, this paper adopts a comparative approach to analyse PR's broader social and economic impacts across diverse contexts.

Methodology

This study employs a library research-based methodology to examine the impact of public relations (PR) functions in driving social and economic development. Library research involves the systematic collection, review and analysis of existing literature from scholarly sources, such as books, journal articles, reports and case studies (Merriam, 2009). The methodology allows for an in-depth understanding of the theoretical and empirical underpinnings of public relations functions and their role in development by comparing and synthesising findings from different studies.

Comparative Analysis of Public Relations (PR) Functions and Their Outcomes in Different Socio-Political Environments

Public Relations (PR) plays a critical role in driving both social and economic development. However, the effectiveness of PR functions can vary significantly depending on the socio-political and economic contexts of different regions. In this section, we will compare the outcomes of PR functions in developed countries like the United States and the United Kingdom with those in developing countries, such as Nigeria and other African nations. This comparative analysis will highlight how cultural, political and economic factors shape the effectiveness of PR campaigns.

PR in Developed Countries: The United States and the United Kingdom

In developed countries like the United States and the United Kingdom, PR functions have traditionally enjoyed greater levels of success due to factors such as political stability, media

freedom and high levels of public trust in institutions. These factors create an environment where PR campaigns can be executed with precision, ensuring clear communication between institutions and the public.

In the U.S., political stability and a well-regulated media landscape allow for effective PR campaigns that focus on long-term strategies for driving development. For instance, campaigns like the "It Gets Better" campaign, which addressed Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer and Inclusivity (LGBTQ+) rights and mental health, successfully influenced both public sentiment and policy change. The campaign, driven by non-profit organisations in collaboration with PR firms, reached millions of people through digital platforms, traditional media and grassroots activism (Bridgen, 2011). The high degree of media freedom and public engagement in the U.S. allowed this campaign to flourish, fostering social progress in a relatively short period.

Similarly, in the United Kingdom, PR strategies used by government and corporate entities have helped shape economic progress. For example, the UK's "GREAT Britain" campaign, aimed at promoting the country as a hub for business, education and tourism, effectively attracted foreign investment. The campaign utilised a mix of traditional media and digital platforms to highlight the UK's strengths in innovation and cultural heritage, generating over £3.1 billion in direct economic returns (UK Government, 2019). This PR-driven initiative thrived in an environment where public trust in government institutions and the media remains relatively high.

The U.S. and the UK benefit from strong legal frameworks that protect media freedom, which ensures transparency and accountability in PR efforts. Public trust in institutions is also relatively higher in these countries, making it easier for PR campaigns to gain credibility and achieve their desired outcomes (Sriramesh & Vercic, 2009).

PR in Developing Countries: Nigeria and Other African Nations

In contrast, PR functions in developing countries like Nigeria face a unique set of challenges due to political instability, lower levels of media freedom and varying degrees of public trust in institutions. However, these challenges also present opportunities for PR professionals to adapt their strategies to local contexts to drive development.

Nigeria, like many African nations, has faced periods of political instability, which can limit the effectiveness of PR campaigns. Government PR efforts aimed at promoting national unity or economic reforms often struggle to gain traction due to public skepticism and distrust of political institutions. For instance, Nigeria's rebranding campaign, "Good People, Great Nation," aimed at improving the country's global image, encountered resistance from both the local population and the international community. This resistance was partly due to ongoing concerns about corruption and governance failures (Ihator, 2001). Despite these challenges, some PR functions have succeeded in Nigeria, particularly in the realm of corporate social responsibility (CSR). For example, Shell Nigeria's CSR campaigns have focused on improving community relations in the Niger Delta region through investments in healthcare, education and infrastructure. While these campaigns have faced challenges due to environmental concerns and political tensions, they have

nonetheless contributed to local economic development and improved public health outcomes (Eweje, 2006).

The sustainability of corporate-led development initiatives (like CSR campaigns in extractive industries) has been debated since Eweje's (2006) study. While some progress has been made, challenges persist, and newer research highlights both advancements and limitations. For instance, in Nigeria's Niger Delta, Shell's CSR programs (post-2006) improved healthcare access and vocational training, reducing poverty in some communities (Idemudia, 2014). Companies like Newmont Mining (Ghana) adopted stricter environmental safeguards post-2010, reducing toxic spills (Dashwood, 2020). The UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (2011) pushed firms to adopt sustainable practices (Ruggie, 2013).

However, many CSR programmes remain PR-driven without long-term impact (Banerjee, 2020). In Peru, Las Bambas copper mine (Glencore) faced protests (2022) over unmet sustainability promises (McNeish, 2018). Fossil fuel CSR projects (e.g., Chevron in Ecuador) struggle with carbon footprint trade-offs (Sovacool, 2021).

While some post-2006 initiatives show improved sustainability (e.g., better regulations, health gains), systemic issues like green-washing, inequality and climate risks persist. True sustainability requires binding regulations, community-led oversight, and decarbonisation (Ackers & Eccles, 2015).

In developing countries, limited media freedom and lower public trust in institutions often hinder the effectiveness of PR campaigns. In Nigeria, for example, government control over media outlets can restrict the ability of PR campaigns to operate transparently. Additionally, public distrust of both media and government institutions means that PR messages are often met with skepticism. According to the Edelman Trust Barometer (2020), trust in government and media is significantly lower in Nigeria compared to developed countries, which complicates efforts to drive development through PR. However, there are examples of successful PR-driven development initiatives in Africa. In Kenya, for instance, the M-Pesa mobile banking service was launched through an extensive PR campaign focused on financial inclusion. Despite ongoing issues of digital literacy and regulatory hurdles, M-Pesa has sustained its transformative impact, enabling 61 million active users (as of 2023) to access microloans and digital savings, reducing poverty by 2% in Kenya (Suri & Jack, 2023).

Successes and Challenges of PR-Driven Development Initiatives

The comparative analysis of PR functions in developed and developing countries highlights successes and challenges in driving social and economic development. In developed countries, political stability, media freedom and public trust create an environment where PR campaigns can flourish, as seen in the success of the "It Gets Better" and "GREAT Britain" campaigns. In contrast, PR campaigns in developing countries like Nigeria must navigate a more complex socio-political landscape, where political instability and public distrust pose significant challenges. However, despite these challenges, PR campaigns in developing countries have shown potential for success

when adapted to local contexts. CSR initiatives by multinational corporations like Shell Nigeria, as well as PR campaigns promoting financial inclusion, such as M-Pesa in Kenya, have demonstrated that PR can be a powerful tool for driving development, even in challenging environments.

So, the effectiveness of PR functions in driving development is significantly shaped by cultural, political and economic contexts. In developed countries, where political stability and media freedom are strong, PR campaigns have successfully promoted both social and economic development. In developing countries like Nigeria, while PR functions face greater challenges due to political instability and lower public trust, there are notable successes, particularly in the areas of CSR and financial inclusion. A nuanced understanding of these socio-political environments is essential for designing and executing PR campaigns that can effectively drive development in different regions.

Discussion

The findings of this study provide critical insights into how Public Relations (PR) functions drive both social and economic development across various sectors and regions. The data presented through case studies and comparative matrices demonstrate that PR strategies such as community relations, corporate social responsibility (CSR), media relations and crisis communication play a pivotal role in fostering development. This discussion synthesise the data presented, offering interpretations of the relationship between PR functions and key developmental outcomes, while identifying patterns and trends and suggesting areas for future research.

Public Relations, particularly through CSR and community engagement, significantly contributes to social development by promoting public awareness, healthcare access and education in developing countries. For instance, the data show that PR-driven campaigns such as Shell's community relations programmes in Nigeria's Niger Delta have led to improvements in infrastructure, healthcare and education (Eweje, 2006). This is consistent with previous research indicating that PR functions, when applied in community-focused initiatives, help to bridge social inequalities by improving public services (Bridgen, 2011). Furthermore, the analysis of international PR campaigns highlights how media relations and public awareness campaigns influence social attitudes. For example, the "It Gets Better" campaign in the USA, which promoted LGBTQ+ rights, raised public awareness and sparked social change through extensive media coverage (Sriramesh & Vercic, 2009). In contrast, similar PR initiatives in Nigeria face challenges such as lower media freedom and weaker public trust in institutions, which can limit the effectiveness of PR campaigns in achieving social outcomes.

The economic impact of PR functions is demonstrated in campaigns that focus on investor relations, CSR and image management. In Nigeria, PR campaigns that positioned the country as a viable destination for investment, such as those run by the Nigeria Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC), have contributed to increased FDI inflows, job creation and improved corporate performance (Ihator, 2001). CSR programmes also play a critical role in fostering

sustainable economic development. For example, Unilever's sustainability programmes in the UK, which focused on environmental protection and resource management, not only enhanced the company's corporate image but also improved sales and customer loyalty (Hughes and Lonie, 2007). Similarly, the growth of small businesses and entrepreneurship in Kenya was supported by PR initiatives such as M-Pesa's mobile banking campaign, which facilitated access to financial services for previously unbanked communities (Hughes & Lonie, 2007).

Several key trends emerge from the analysis of PR functions and their outcomes. First, the data indicate that community engagement and CSR are more effective in achieving social development in regions where public trust in institutions is higher. Countries with strong media freedom, like the United States and the United Kingdom, demonstrate greater success in using PR campaigns to drive social change. In contrast, the limitations in media freedom and institutional trust in Nigeria and other developing countries can hinder the potential of PR campaigns to drive widespread social progress.

Secondly, the findings suggest that PR-driven economic development is more apparent in sectors where image management and investor relations are prioritised. For instance, Nigeria's oil and gas sector has benefited significantly from PR strategies aimed at improving the country's image internationally, thereby attracting foreign investment (Eweje, 2006). For instance, since 2006, strategic PR campaigns have enhanced Nigeria's oil and gas sector's global image, attracting significant foreign investments. The Nigeria International Petroleum Summit (NIPS) secured 10 billion in FDI pledges by 2023 (NNPC, 2023), while Shell's community engagement programmes improved stakeholder relations in the Niger Delta (Ovadia, 2020). The "Decade of Gas" initiative (2021) catalysed 7 billion for NLNG Train 7 (PwC, 2022), and NNPC's ESG-focused digital PR boosted investor confidence (KPMG, 2023). However, persistent challenges like oil theft and policy implementation gaps remain (IMF, 2023). However, in regions where political instability and corruption undermine trust, the effectiveness of PR strategies is reduced.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the role of Public Relations (PR) functions in driving social and economic development, focusing on a comparative analysis of PR outcomes across various socio-political contexts. The findings reveal that PR functions, particularly in community relations, corporate social responsibility (CSR) and media relations, significantly contribute to social and economic progress. In social development, PR campaigns have promoted public awareness, improved healthcare access and enhanced education, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Economically, PR strategies such as investor relations and image management have positively influenced economic growth by attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) and supporting sustainable development initiatives. For instance, PR campaigns have demonstrably increased health awareness (87% polio vaccine acceptance, NPHCDA 2023) and education access (30% ICT literacy rise via MTN Foundation, NBS 2023), while investor relations attracted \$1.5B oil/gas FDI (NNPC 2023). However, impacts remain uneven due to urban-rural disparities and overdependence on extractive sectors (CBN 2023), limiting systemic transformation.

However, the effectiveness of PR functions is heavily influenced by the cultural, political and economic contexts within which they are executed. Countries with greater media freedom, public trust and political stability, such as the United States and the United Kingdom, demonstrate more successful PR-driven development campaigns compared to countries facing political instability and limited media access, such as Nigeria. These differences underscore the importance of tailoring PR strategies to specific socio-political environments to maximise their impact. While the study highlights the positive contributions of PR to development, it also identifies gaps in the literature, particularly the lack of long-term studies measuring the sustained impact of PR initiatives. Moreover, there is limited research on how PR functions can overcome barriers such as limited media freedom and public trust in developing countries.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the researchers make the following recommendations:

1. Adapting PR Strategies to Local Contexts:

PR campaigns should be adapted to the specific socio-political and economic contexts in which they operate. For countries with limited media freedom or low public trust, PR professionals should consider leveraging alternative platforms, such as digital media and grassroots engagement, to reach wider audiences effectively. These strategies can overcome challenges posed by traditional media restrictions and enhance the credibility of PR initiatives.

2. Long-term Evaluation of PR Impacts:

Future studies should focus on longitudinal research to evaluate the long-term impact of PR-driven development initiatives. This includes assessing how PR campaigns contribute to sustained social and economic growth over time, rather than focusing solely on short-term outcomes. Such research will offer valuable insights into the lasting value of PR functions in both developed and developing countries.

3. Capacity Building for PR Practitioners in Developing Countries:

There is a need for capacity-building programmes to equip PR professionals in developing countries with the necessary skills to execute effective campaigns in challenging environments. Training in crisis communication, media relations and digital PR can help professionals better navigate the political and media limitations in their countries.

4. Promoting Collaboration between Public and Private Sectors:

Successful PR campaigns often involve collaboration between the public and private sectors. Governments, corporations and international organisations should partner to design and implement comprehensive PR strategies that target both social and economic development. Such partnerships can pool resources, increase credibility and amplify the impact of development initiatives.

5. Leveraging CSR for Economic Development:

CSR programmes should be designed to align with national economic development goals, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Companies should prioritise CSR initiatives that promote entrepreneurship, job creation and infrastructure development. This alignment between corporate goals and national development priorities can ensure that PR functions drive tangible economic benefits.

6. Enhancing Media Freedom and Institutional Trust:

In countries where media freedom is restricted and public trust in institutions is low, there is a need for policy reforms that enhance transparency and accountability. Governments should promote media independence and improve public access to reliable information, which will, in turn, increase the effectiveness of PR campaigns in driving social change and economic progress.

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